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Performance Optimization of Control Applications on Fog Computing Platforms Using Scheduling and Isolation

MOHAMMADREZA BARZEGARAN¹, ANTON CERVIN², (Member, IEEE),
AND PAUL POP¹, (Member, IEEE)

¹Department of Applied Mathematics and Computer Science, Technical University of Denmark, 2800 Kongens Lyngby, Denmark

²Department of Automatic Control, Lund University, 221 00 Lund, Sweden

Corresponding author: Mohammadreza Barzegaran (mohba@dtu.dk)

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ABSTRACT In this paper, we address mixed-criticality applications characterized by their safety criticality and time-dependent performance, which are virtualized on a Fog Computing Platform (*FCP*). The *FCP* is implemented as a set of interconnected multicore computing nodes, and brings computation and communication closer to the edge of the network, where the machines are located in industrial applications. We use partitioning and static-cyclic scheduling to provide isolation among mixed-criticality tasks and to guarantee their timing requirements. The temporal and spatial isolation is enforced via partitions, which execute tasks with the same criticality level. We consider that the tasks are scheduled using static cyclic scheduling. We are interested in determining the mapping of tasks to the cores of the fog nodes, the assignment of tasks to the partitions, the partition schedule tables, and the tasks' schedule tables, such that the Quality-of-Control for the control tasks is maximized and we meet the timing requirements for all tasks, including tasks with lower-criticality levels. We are also interested in determining the periods for control tasks to balance the schedulability and the control performance. We have proposed a Simulated Annealing metaheuristic, which relies on a heuristic algorithm for determining the schedules and partitions, to solve this optimization problem. Our optimization strategy has been evaluated on several test cases, showing the effectiveness of the proposed method.

INDEX TERMS Fog computing, mixed-criticality systems, quality-of-control, scheduling, partitioning, optimization.

I. INTRODUCTION

We are at the beginning of a new industrial revolution, i.e., Industry 4.0, which is underpinned by a digital transformation that will affect all industries. Industry 4.0 will bring increased productivity and flexibility, mass customization, reduced time-to-market, improved product quality, innovations and new business models. However, Industry 4.0 will only become a reality through the convergence of Operational and Information Technologies (*OT & IT*), which use different computation and communication technologies. *OT* consists of cyber-physical systems that monitor and control physical processes that manage, e.g., automated manufacturing, crit-

ical infrastructures, smart buildings and smart cities. These application areas are typically safety critical and real-time, requiring guaranteed extra-functional properties, such as, real-time behavior, reliability, availability, industry-specific safety standards, and security.

OT uses proprietary solutions imposing severe restrictions on the information flow. *IT* such as Cloud Computing cannot be used at the edge of the network, where industrial machines are located, and where very stringent extra-functional properties have to be guaranteed [1]. Instead, a new paradigm, called *Fog Computing*, is envisioned as an architectural means to realize the *IT/OT* convergence. Fog Computing is a "system-level architecture that distributes resources and services of computing, storage, control and networking anywhere along the continuum from Cloud to Things" [2]. With Fog

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FIGURE 1. Fog Computing platform. Boxes represent fog nodes, connected with each other and to the Cloud; the thick lines are the network. Applications (Apps) run in the fog and Cloud.

Computing, communication devices, such as switches and routers are extended with computational and storage resources to enable a variety of communication and computation options (see Fig. 1).

Fog Computing will enable a powerful convergence, unification and standardization at the networking, security, data, computing, and control levels. It will lead to improved interoperability, security, more efficient and rich control, and higher manufacturing efficiency and flexibility [3]. The vision is to virtualize the control (which is implemented as control tasks running on a Fog Computing Platform) and achieve the same level dependability as the one taken for granted in *OT*. Several initiatives are currently working towards realizing this vision [4], [5].

The integration of computational and storage resources into the communication devices is realized in the *fog node* (*FN*). In many applications, including industrial automation and robotics, several layers of *FN*s with differing computation, communication and storage capabilities will evolve, from powerful high-end *FN*s to low-end *FN*s with limited resources. Researches have started to propose solutions for the implementation of *FN*s [3], [4] and fog node solutions have started to be developed by companies [4]–[6].

An *FN* is equipped with computational resources that allows the execution of applications and it is connected to a larger data processing facility like a Cloud environment. Regarding computation, we assume that the control tasks are running in an Real-Time Operating System using real-time scheduling policies (we consider static-cyclic scheduling in this paper), and the control applications are separated in different *partitions* enforced using hardware-supported virtualization, based on hypervisors, such as ACRN [7] or PikeOS [8]. *FN*s could be connected to each others and to the machines through a deterministic communication solution, such as IEEE 802.1 Time-Sensitive Networking (TSN) [9], see Fig. 1. Such a Fog Computing Platform (*FCP*) allows to increase the spatial distance between the physical process and

the *FN* that controls it, allowing the control functions can be executed remotely on the *FN*. However, the way the *FCP* is configured has an impact on the control performance of the control applications.

Given a set of mixed-criticality applications and an *FCP*, we are interested to determine an *FCP* configuration such that the Quality-of-Control (*QoC*) of control tasks is maximized and all the tasks meet their deadlines. Determining an *FCP* configuration means deciding on the partitions, the mapping of tasks to the *FN*s and partitions, the schedule table for tasks, the partition table for partitions, and the periods of control tasks. We do not address the scheduling of messages on the TSN network, which can be solved with approaches such as [10] that achieve low latency and zero jitter.

A. CONTRIBUTIONS

This paper shows that when control becomes virtualized, implemented as tasks on an *FCP*, the configuration of the *FCP* has a strong impact on the control performance. We formulate the *FCP* configuration as an optimization problem, and we have proposed a metaheuristic solution to solve it. Compared to the related work (see Sect. VII), which has addressed the scheduling of tasks to maximize *QoC*, we also optimize the partitioning, which is required in an *FCP* to provide isolation among mixed-criticality applications, decide on the mapping of tasks to partitions, consider the preemption of tasks to make static schedules more flexible, and determine the period of control tasks to trade-off *QoC* and schedulability of non-control tasks. In addition, we also consider a more realistic model of control applications and provide more accurate measure of *QoC* compared to previous work, see Sect. IV.

B. OUTLINE OF THE PAPER

In the remainder of this paper, we give the models for application and architecture of the system in Sect. II. The problem is formulated in Sect. III. We give an introduction to control theory in Sect. IV. In Sect. V, we present the details of our proposed optimization strategy with an illustrative example. Our optimization approach is evaluated in Sect. VI on several test cases. The related work is covered in Sect. VII and Sect. VIII concludes the paper.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

This section presents the architecture and application models. Table.1 summarizes the notations used in the system model.

A. ARCHITECTURE MODEL

There have been several *FN* architectures proposed, and some of them are commercially realized [4]–[6], [11], [12]. A possible *FN* architecture targeting mixed-criticality applications, is presented in Fig. 2. Such an architecture is similar to several *FN* architectures prepared for industrial applications [4], [6]. We model the architecture as a set of *FN*s, denoted by \mathcal{N} . Each *FN*, $N_i \in \mathcal{N}$, has a set of cores \mathcal{P}_i , and each core is denoted with $P_j \in \mathcal{P}_i$. An example architecture with two *FN*s

TABLE 1. Summary of notations.

Symbol	Fog Computing Platform (FCP)
\mathcal{N}	Set of all Fog Nodes
$N_i (\mathcal{P}_i) \in \mathcal{N}$	Fog Node (<i>FN</i>)
\mathcal{P}_i	Set of all cores in the Fog Node N_i
$P_j \in \mathcal{P}_i$	Core
\mathfrak{P}	Set of all cores in the platform
Δ	Set of all partitions
$\delta_i (L_i, \xi_i) \in \Delta$	Partition
L_i	Criticality level of a partition
ξ_i	Overhead time of a partition
\mathcal{V}	Set of partition tables
$v_i \in \mathcal{V}$	Partition table
\mathcal{S}	Set of schedule tables
$s_i \in \mathcal{S}$	Schedule table
Γ	Set of all applications
$\gamma_i \in \Gamma$	Set of tasks of application γ_i
\mathcal{F}_i	Set of possible periods for an application
\mathcal{F}	The application mapping function to periods
$\tau_i (D_i, T_i, L_i, C_i) \in \gamma_j$	Task
D_i	Deadline of a task
T_i	Period of a task
L_i	Criticality level of the application γ_j
C_i	Set of WCETs for the application γ_j
\mathcal{M}	The task mapping function to the cores
\mathcal{O}	The task assignment function to the partitions

FIGURE 2. Fog node architecture. The software stack is running on a multicore, and has, from bottom to top, a hypervisor, partitions running OSes, middleware and tasks.

is presented in Fig. 3. The *FNs* have respectively two and one cores. Sensors and actuators are connected to *FNs* with network switches. The lines represent network links.

Mixed-criticality applications sharing the same platform have to be isolated from each other, otherwise a faulty lower-criticality task may interfere with a higher-criticality task, leading to failure. We assume that the applications are isolated from each other using spatial and temporal partitioning [13], implemented via hypervisors such as ACRN [7], Xen [14], PikeOS [8] or XtratuM [15].

We denote the set of partitions with Δ . Each partition $\delta_i \in \Delta$, is characterized by a criticality level L_i . For example

FIGURE 3. Example architecture with two *FNs*.

L_i can represent the Safety Integrity Levels (SIL) of an application, which has values from 0, non-critical, to 4, highest criticality [16]. A partition δ_i , scheduled on multiple cores, consists of several partition slices that are time slots to which the processor is assigned for the partition. We assume that the partitions are statically scheduled via partition tables, denoted with \mathcal{V} , (e.g, as used in Xen or PikeOS), which allocate processing cores from an *FN* to partitions in partition slices. A partition table repeats periodically with a system cycle. Switching among partition slices imposes an overhead. This overhead depends on the computing platform, the hypervisor, see [17] for a description of overheads in Xen, and may also depend on the contents of the partition. For example in [18], researchers assume that the overhead is 5% of the maximum worst-case execution time (WCET) of the tasks allocated to a partition. Our model is general, and assumes a partition-dependent overhead denoted with ξ_i for each partition δ_i .

Real-time applications can be implemented with time-triggered or event-triggered scheduling policies. In this paper, we assume that the scheduling policy is static cyclic scheduling [19] (also known as time-triggered scheduling), which has been shown to be suitable for critical control applications. We will consider event-triggered scheduling in our future work. The set of all schedule tables in the model are denoted with \mathcal{S} . A schedule table $s_i \in \mathcal{S}$, captures the start and finishing time of tasks. We consider that within a schedule table, a task may be split into several parts, similar to run-time preemption in preemptive scheduling, but decided at design time. This has been shown to improve flexibility, schedulability [20] and *QoC* for control tasks [21]. The preemption threshold can be controlled by a parameter called macrotick, which specifies the granularity of preemption [22].

Fig. 4 shows an example of partition tables \mathcal{V} and schedule tables \mathcal{S} using a Gantt chart. In this example, we assume that mixed-criticality applications with a total of ten tasks are executing on two cores, which have four partitions Δ . All tasks in a partition have the same criticality level. The partitions δ_1 , δ_2 , δ_3 , and δ_4 have the criticality level of

three tasks with precedence constraints. The application γ_2 has a set of possible periods F_2 .

III. PROBLEM FORMULATION

We formulate the problem as follows: Given (i) a set of applications Γ and (ii) a set of *FNs* \mathcal{N} , we want to determine a configuration Ψ consisting of: (1) a set of partitions Δ , (2) a mapping \mathcal{M} of the tasks to cores, (3) an assignment \mathcal{O} of tasks to the partitions, (4) the periods of control applications \mathcal{F} , (5) the partition tables \mathcal{V} , and (6) the schedule tables \mathcal{S} such that:

- 1) **Maximum control performance is achieved for the critical control applications:** We seek a solution which has the best overall *QoC* for all the control applications. This is realized by minimizing the function \bar{J} captured by Eq. (7), see Sect. V-C.
- 2) **The deviation among the *QoC* of control applications is minimized:** We would like to balance the deviation σ_j , captured by Eq. (8), see Sect. V-C.
- 3) **Temporal isolation is achieved among tasks with different criticality levels:** Each task τ_i and its assigned partition δ_j , captured with the function \mathcal{O} , share the same criticality level.
- 4) **The deadlines for all tasks are met:** Given that all the tasks are periodic and real-time, each task τ_i should be completed before its deadline D_i .

IV. CONTROL THEORY

The mathematical relation between the inputs, outputs and state variables of a dynamical system around an equilibrium point can be modelled as a linear differential equation and denoted by a state-space representation [24]

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{x}(t) &= Ax(t) + Bu(t) + w(t), \\ y(t) &= Cx(t) + Du(t), \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where the vectors x , u , w and y denote the state, the control input, the disturbance input, and the measured output respectively, and where A , B , C and D are matrices of appropriate sizes. The input–output relationship can equivalently be described by a transfer function $G(s)$ [24]. A feedback control system, *FCS*, or simply a control application, samples the output of the dynamical system $y(t)$, calculates the deviation from the desired output $r(t)$ (in this paper generically assumed to be zero), and drives the deviation to zero by applying an appropriate control signal $u(t)$.

A. FEEDBACK CONTROL SYSTEM

An *FCS* can be implemented as a three task application. The source task, let's call it τ_1 , samples the dynamical system by using sensors. The task may process the captured data from sensors. The second task, let's call it τ_2 , uses the output of the task τ_1 to calculate the control signal. The task τ_2 utilizes various methods for the calculation and may be engaged with time-consuming calculation [24]. The implemented method for calculating the control signal is called the control law. The sink task, let's call it τ_3 , uses the output of the task τ_2 to exert

FIGURE 6. A simple *FCS*.

the control signal using the connection with the actuators. A simple *FCS* has an analogue to digital converter for the source task τ_1 , a control law τ_2 , and an analogue to digital converter for the sink task τ_3 . Fig. 6 shows a simple *FCS*.

A control application is typically a periodic application with a known period. The period should be chosen in relation to the speed of the controlled system, and the shorter the period, the faster the controller is able to respond to the typical disturbances. On the other hand, a too short period causes high utilization of resources and leads to problems in resource-constrained computing platforms. A common rule of thumb [25] is to determine the period of the application based on the bandwidth of the closed-loop system. The closed-loop transfer function $H(s)$ is calculated by

$$H(s) = \frac{G(s)K(s)}{1 + G(s)K(s)}, \quad (2)$$

where $G(s)$ and $K(s)$ are the transfer functions of the dynamical system and the feedback controller respectively [24]. The sampling period T is then chosen in the interval

$$\frac{0.2}{\omega_b} \leq T \leq \frac{0.6}{\omega_b}, \quad (3)$$

where ω_b is the 3 dB bandwidth of $H(s)$ [25].

As discussed, choosing the period from the interval has two impacts; first, stability and robustness of controller and last, resource utilization and schedulability. Our optimization strategy will determine the periods \mathcal{F} to strike a compromise between their impacts.

The task timing is a source of additional disturbances for a control application. Ideally, the controller should execute without timing variations (jitter) and with as short delay as possible between the sensor task and the actuator task. A time delay has the direct consequence of decreasing the phase margin of the control system, which means worse performance and less robustness. Jitter is the deviation from the true periodic timing of an event, and its effects on the control performance are less obvious to analyze. In a control application, the event can be the execution of a task or the receiving of a network message.

The execution of a task is a periodic event of which instances are characterized by start time, duration and end

FIGURE 7. Step response of a sample control loop.

time. Jitters can be associated with the start time, the end time and the duration. It is also associated either among all instances or two consecutive instances. The data packets to/from actuators/sensors are also periodic events which are characterized by send-time, transmit-time and receive-time which are vulnerable to jitter. While we are ignoring the communication in this paper, delays and jitter are only applied to tasks. The jitter of a task is either measured among all the instances (absolute) or two consecutive instances (relative). We categorize jitters as follows:

- **Start Jitter** of a task is the maximum deviation of the arrivals of instances of a task.
- **Release Jitter** of a task is the maximum deviation of the worst-case delay between the arrivals of instances of a task and their release times.
- **End Jitter** of a task is the maximum deviation of the release time of instances of a task.
- **Input-Output Jitter** is the maximum deviation of the worst-case delay between sampling from a cyber-physical system and exerting the actuation to it among the instances of tasks in a control loop. This type of jitter covers both timing of communication links from and to sensors and actuators, and the execution of the control tasks.

B. CONTROL DESIGN

While designing an *FCS*, there is a trade-off between accuracy and rapidity of the control loop. The trade-off is called the control performance. It is determined by several parameters such as the damping ratio, the phase margin and the gain margin, see [24] for more details. These parameters help control engineers to find the suitable control law and tune the control law to get the intended performance. The accuracy and rapidity is depicted in the transient and steady state response of the control loop. Fig. 7 shows the transient and steady state step-response of a sample control loop with notation of associated parameters (rise-time T_{rise} , peak-time T_{peak} , settling-time $T_{settling}$ and steady state error).

The rise-time T_{rise} is defined as the time takes for the output response to reach 90% of the input value. The rise-time shows how fast the controller can react to the disturbances exerted

to the dynamical system. The peak response is defined as highest out-put response the controller reached before the desired value. The peak plays an important role in the robustness of the controller against disturbances. The settling-time $T_{settling}$ is defined as the time takes for the output response to reach 98% of the input value. The settling-time shows how fast the controller can reach to the desired state. The steady-state error shows the minimum deviation of the controller output response from the desired state. It shows the accuracy of the controller.

The various aspects of the control loop performance can be captured in a cost function. A common choice [26] is to use a quadratic cost function of the form

$$J = \int_0^{\infty} \left(x^T(t)Q_1x(t) + u^T(t)Q_2u(t) \right) dt, \quad (4)$$

where the weighting matrices Q_1 and Q_2 tell how much deviations in the different states and the control input should be penalized. By proper tuning of the cost function, the desired transient and steady-state behaviour can be achieved in the control design. The same cost function can also be used to evaluate the performance of the controller under non-ideal circumstances. A larger value of the cost J then means that the response is more sluggish or more oscillatory, typically increasing the settling time of the system.

Given a linear system description by Eq. (1) and a quadratic cost function in Eq. (4), an optimal controller known as a linear-quadratic-Gaussian (LQG) controller can be calculated [24]. The above formulation is given in continuous time, but the LQG design methodology can also handle a large number of other conditions, such as sampled design [25] and compensation for time delays [27]. The Jitterbug toolbox [28], utilized in this paper to design control applications, has support for designing an optimal sampled LQG controller that compensates for either a fixed or a random input-output delay with a given probability distribution.

C. CALCULATION OF CONTROL PERFORMANCE

In this paper, we use JITTERTIME [29] to calculate the QoC with the cost function J , defined in Eq. (4). JITTERTIME takes the schedule tables \mathcal{S} and partition tables \mathcal{V} and calculates the cost J . The tables \mathcal{S} contain the starting and finishing time of the tasks. JITTERTIME simulates the behaviour of a control application with the given starting and finishing times of control tasks and evaluates the behaviour using the quadratic cost function in Eq. (4).

The cost J decreases under the circumstances in which the Input-Output Jitter of a control application (defined in Sect. IV-A) as well as the end-to-end response of the control application decreases. The end-to-end response of a control application is the delay between the sampling from a cyber-physical system and exerting the actuation to it. In our problem, the delay is between the starting of the sensor task to the finishing of the actuator task. More information about the inner workings of JITTERTIME can be found in [29].

V. SOLUTION

The problem we are addressing in this paper is interactable. Finding a solution to our problem involves deciding on the schedule tables, which has been shown to be Non-deterministic Polynomial time (NP)-complete in the strong sense [30]. For such problems, exact optimization methods such as Brunch & Bound, Integer Linear Programming and Constraint Programming have exponential efforts. Hence, we propose a Simulated Annealing (SA)-based metaheuristic [31] to solve this optimization problem. Metaheuristics do not guarantee finding the optimal solution, but have been shown to find good quality solutions for a wide range of practical applications [31].

We have decided to divide the problem such that the schedule synthesis is performed separately within the SA using a scheduling heuristic. List Scheduling [32] is a typical heuristic that derives good quality solutions, but it cannot easily handle applications with multiple periods and preemption. Instead, inspired by [22], we have proposed a scheduling heuristic based on the simulation of an Earliest Deadline First (EDF) algorithm, which can handle both multiple periods and preemption.

An overview of our proposed Fog Computing Platform Configuration (FCPC) optimization strategy is shown in Alg.1. The SA decides the period of the control applications, the mapping of tasks to cores in the FCP. The assignment of tasks to partitions and the partition and schedule tables are decided by our EDF-based Scheduling and Partitioning Heuristics (SPH, called in Alg.1). SA also decides parameters that influence the scheduling in SPH, such as task offsets Θ and relative deadlines Φ used for the EDF simulation.

SA is presented in Sect. V-A and SPH in Sect. V-B. The objective function used for the optimization is presented in Sect. V-C. SA uses design transformation to explore the search space, and these are presented in Sect. V-D. Sect. V-E has an example that illustrates how our proposed FCPC strategy works.

A. SIMULATED ANNEALING

SA (line 7–17 in Alg. 1) starts from an initial solution (line 4) and iterates to search the solution space (line 7–17). The initial solution assigns the period of each control task to the minimum value in its set of periods \mathcal{F} , assigns the offsets Θ of tasks to zero, and sets the relative deadline Φ of all tasks to their deadline values. The initial mapping \mathcal{M} is obtained by a greedy approach i.e., each task is mapped iteratively to the core that has the smaller utilization in that iteration. The initial assignment of tasks to partitions \mathcal{O} is defined such that each application has a partition for its criticality level on each core where the application has a task mapped. The partition tables \mathcal{V} and schedule tables \mathcal{S} are obtained with our Scheduling and Partitioning Heuristic (SPH), called inside the InitialSolution function.

In each iteration, SA uses design transformations (or *moves*) to generate neighboring solutions starting from the

Algorithm 1 $\Psi = \langle \mathcal{M}, \mathcal{O}, \mathcal{S}, \mathcal{V}, \mathcal{F} \rangle = FCPC(\Gamma, \mathcal{N})$

```

1:  $i \leftarrow 0$ 
2:  $t \leftarrow T_{start}$ 
3:  $\Theta \leftarrow \{0\}; \Phi \leftarrow \{D_i\}$ 
4:  $\Psi \leftarrow \text{InitialSolution}(\Gamma, \mathcal{N})$ 
5:  $J \leftarrow \text{JITTERTIME}(\mathcal{S}, \mathcal{V}, \Gamma)$ 
6:  $\Omega \leftarrow \text{CostFunction}(J, \mathcal{S})$ 
7: repeat
8:    $\langle \mathcal{M}_i, \mathcal{F}_i, \Theta_i, \Phi_i \rangle \leftarrow \text{Neighbor}(\Psi, \Gamma, \mathcal{N})$ 
9:    $\langle \mathcal{S}_i, \mathcal{V}_i \rangle \leftarrow \text{SPH}(\mathcal{M}_i, \mathcal{F}_i, \Theta_i, \Phi_i, \Gamma, \mathcal{N})$ 
10:   $J_i \leftarrow \text{JITTERTIME}(\mathcal{S}_i, \mathcal{V}_i, \Gamma)$ 
11:   $\Omega_i \leftarrow \text{CostFunction}(J_i, \mathcal{S}_i)$ 
12:   $\lambda \leftarrow \Omega_i - \Omega$ 
13:  if  $\lambda < 0$  or  $\text{random}[0, 1) < \text{Prob}(\lambda, t)$  then
14:     $\Psi \leftarrow \Psi_i; \Theta \leftarrow \Theta_i; \Phi \leftarrow \Phi_i$ 
15:  end if
16:   $t \leftarrow t \times \alpha$ 
17: until stopping criterion is True
18: return  $\Psi = \langle \mathcal{M}, \mathcal{O}, \mathcal{S}, \mathcal{V}, \mathcal{F} \rangle$ 

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current solution Ψ (line 8). The generated neighborhood is evaluated with the cost function Ω , defined in Sect. V-C. In each iteration, the algorithm compares the cost Ω_i of the generated neighborhood with the cost Ω of the current solution (line 13).

SA accepts a solution if the cost is improved. SA may also accept a worse-quality solution (in the hope to better explore the solution space) with a certain probability:

$$\text{Prob}(\lambda, t) = e^{-\frac{\lambda}{t}}, \quad (5)$$

where λ is the difference between cost of the generated neighborhood and cost of the current solution (line 12). The probability to accept worse solutions decreases with time according to a “cooling schedule”, where t is the current temperature. SA starts from an initial temperature T_{start} (line 2), and cools down in each iteration at the rate of α (line 16). The search terminates when a stopping criterion has been satisfied (line 17), e.g., no improvement after a given number of iterations, a temperature of zero or a time limit was reached.

B. SCHEDULING AND PARTITIONING HEURISTIC (SPH)

Our proposed Scheduling and Partitioning Heuristic (SPH) is presented in Alg.2 and takes as input a mapping \mathcal{M} , a set of periods \mathcal{F} , a set offsets Θ , a set of relative-deadlines Φ , the set of applications Γ , and the set of FNs \mathcal{N} . The main idea of SPH is to create first a schedule table for the tasks considering the mapping fixed by SA, and then to post-process the schedule table to derive the partitions and the allocation of tasks to the partition slices. Thus, SPH has two parts, the first part schedules the tasks (line 2–10) and the second part (line 11–13) groups the tasks together to form partitions. During the construction of the schedule table in the first phase, the SPH does not consider the partitioning.

As mentioned earlier, to derive the schedule tables \mathcal{S} , we perform at design time an EDF simulation. The output of that

Algorithm 2 $\langle \mathcal{O}, \mathcal{S}, \mathcal{V} \rangle = SPH(\mathcal{M}, \mathcal{F}, \Theta, \Phi, \Gamma, \mathcal{N})$

```

1:  $H \leftarrow \text{HyperPeriod}(\Gamma)$ 
2:  $Q_{jobs} \leftarrow \text{CreateJobs}(\Gamma, H)$ 
3:  $t \leftarrow 0$ 
4: repeat
5:   for all  $\partial$  in  $Q_{jobs}$  ready at  $t$  do
6:      $\partial_H \leftarrow \text{GetHighestPriority}(\partial)$ 
7:      $\mathcal{X} \leftarrow \text{Schedule}(\partial_H)$ 
8:   end for
9:    $t \leftarrow \text{NextEvent}(Q_{jobs}, t)$ 
10: until  $t < H$ 
11:  $\chi \leftarrow \text{GroupTasks}(\mathcal{X}, \Gamma)$ 
12:  $\mathcal{S} \leftarrow \text{GenerateScheduleTable}(\chi)$ 
13:  $\mathcal{V} \leftarrow \text{GeneratePartitionTable}(\chi)$ 
14: return  $\langle \mathcal{O}, \mathcal{S}, \mathcal{V} \rangle$ 

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simulation is the set of schedules \mathcal{S} . In the simulation, we consider that the duration of each task is its WCET. With *EDF*, a task has the highest priority (and will be scheduled on its respective core) if its deadline D_i comes earlier considering the current time. The outcome \mathcal{S} of a simulation is controlled by Θ , the tasks offsets (their initial earliest activation) and Φ , the relative deadlines used for each task in the simulation. These are modified for each task τ_i by our *SA* in Alg. 1, in the ranges D_i to T_i for the offsets Θ and 0 to D_i for the relative deadlines Φ . Our *EDF* simulation allows preemption (a higher priority task that is ready for execution may interrupt a lower priority task) considering the given macrotick, and can handle data dependencies, i.e. a task will not start before its predecessors have finished executing.

The *EDF* simulation is performed for the duration of a hyperperiod H (which is also the system cycle), defined as the Least Common Multiple of all the task periods (line 1). SPH starts by creating a queue Q_{jobs} with jobs of the tasks in Γ that have to run during H (line 2). Note that in our implementation these jobs are created on the fly, based on events occurring during the simulation. These events are generated by our simulation at design time, as part of the simulation used to derive the schedules. The simulation is performed in lines 4–10. Because SPH is run in each iteration of *SA*, we have optimized its implementation for speed, efficiency, simulation events and skipping only to events that have relevance for building the schedule tables \mathcal{S} . In the following, we explain how the simulation works in principle.

The simulation takes those jobs ∂ from Q_{jobs} that are ready to execute at the time t (line 5) and sorts them based on their priority (line 6). The job which has the earliest deadline and its precedent jobs are arrived, has the highest priority. The high-priority job is denoted with ∂_H . If the priority of ∂_H is higher than the currently executing job, SPH preempts it and schedule ∂_H instead (line 7). The simulation is stored in \mathcal{X} . SPH determines the next time in which a job becomes ready (line 9), considering the remainder of jobs in Q_{jobs} and the macrotick parameter mentioned in Sect. II-A, which controls the granularity of preemption.

The final part of SPH post-processes the simulation data structure \mathcal{X} . SPH groups the time-wise consecutive jobs which have the same criticality level to form partitions, and also delays the tasks to insert the required task switching (in case preemptions were introduced) and partition overheads ξ_i (line 11). See Sect. V-E for an illustration on how our heuristic works to create partitions by grouping tasks. SPH extracts the schedule tables \mathcal{S} from the simulation χ (line 12), and the partition tables \mathcal{V} (line 13).

C. COST FUNCTION

In this section, we define the weighted cost function Ω in Eq.(6), used by our FCPC optimization strategy. The function has three terms (*QoC*, deviation of *QoC* and task schedulability constraint, respectively) and takes the *QoC* of control applications J and the schedule tables \mathcal{S} as input. The *QoC* optimization is controlled by the weights β_1 and β_2 , whereas β_3 is a penalty value for the case when task deadlines are missed. The weights allow the system engineer to control the search for schedulable solutions that optimize *QoC*. Larger values for β_1 and β_2 will drive the search to optimize *QoC*, whereas a larger value for β_3 will drive the search faster to schedulable solutions.

$$\Omega = \beta_1 \times \bar{J} + \beta_2 \times \sigma_J + \beta_3 \times \Lambda \quad (6)$$

The control performance of control applications is captured by the first term. Assuming m number of control applications, the average *QoC* for the applications is

$$\bar{J} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^m J_i}{m}, \quad (7)$$

where, J_i is the *QoC* for a control application γ_i which is calculated by *JITTERTIME* and its value is mapped to the range $[0, 1]$. The range of cost performance is from 0, for the best-performance, to 1, for the worst-performance, e.g., which is unstable. \bar{J} is normalized to the same range.

The second term captures the deviation among the *QoC* of the control applications, and is defined in Eq. (8). Concerning the range of J , the range of variation is from 0, for the equally distributed *QoC* of control applications, to $\sqrt{\frac{m-1}{m}} < 1$ for m control applications when their performance costs are highly-deviated.

$$\sigma_J = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^m |J_i - \bar{J}|}{m}} \quad (8)$$

The last term is the function Λ , which is a constraint that checks for deadline violations for all the tasks in the schedule table. Λ is also normalized, and starts from 0, for no deadline violations, to 1, for the case in which all the jobs have missed their deadlines.

D. SA DESIGN TRANSFORMATIONS

As mentioned earlier, *SA* decide the mapping \mathcal{M} of tasks to the core, assignment \mathcal{O} of tasks to partitions, and periods \mathcal{F} of control applications. The *SA* also varies the offsets of tasks

TABLE 2. Illustrative example applications.

Application	Tasks	L	WCET (ms)	T (ms)	D (ms)
γ_1 $F_1 = \{6, 8, 10, 12\}$	τ_1	3	2	F_1	12
	τ_2	3	1	F_1	12
	τ_3	3	1	F_1	12
γ_2	τ_4	1	5	20	20
	τ_5	1	2	10	10
γ_3	τ_6	2	1	5	5
	τ_7	2	1	10	10
γ_4 $F_4 = \{5, 8, 10, 12\}$	τ_8	3	0.5	F_4	12
	τ_9	3	1	F_4	12
	τ_{10}	3	0.5	F_4	12
γ_5	τ_{11}	0	1	12	12
	τ_{12}	0	1	9	9

The overhead times for these partitions are determined as $100 \mu s$, $50 \mu s$, $100 \mu s$ and $50 \mu s$, respectively (we use the approach from [18], which considers the partition overheads of 5% of the largest task WCET in the partition). Regarding the task switching overheads, we use the values measured in [22]. SPH may delay the tasks to apply these overheads, hence several instances of tasks may miss their deadlines. For example, the task τ_3 will miss its deadline at $t = 16$ ms for about $550 \mu s$.

Let us consider that CONF/S is the current solution driving the search performed by SA in Alg. 1, and this SA perform a ‘‘Swap Task’’ design transformation in line. 8, which results in swapping the mapping of tasks τ_4 and τ_5 . This will result in the configuration from Fig. 8c, which we call CONF/SM (from configuration with separation and mapping), which is feasible, i.e., there are no deadline misses. As a consequence of the task swapping, not only mapping of the tasks to the cores are swapped but also their assignments to the partitions, since they have the same criticality level. In this configuration, the control application γ_1 experiences maximum I/O jitter (12.5% of its period, which is 8 ms) and the control application γ_4 has no I/O jitter (release and start jitters are seen at $t = 10$ ms and $t = 16$ ms). The cost of control is calculated by JITTERTIME, and the average of the two control applications is 0.09642 and the deviation is equal to 0.0388. The cost function, calculated as in Eq. (6) considering a value of 1 for all weights, has a value of 0.13522.

SA will accept the configuration in Fig. 8c as the current solution, since it improves over Fig. 8b that had deadline misses (line 13 in Alg. 1). Let us assume that the next design transformation is done by ‘‘Period Selection’’, e.g., by selecting the period of 10 ms for tasks in the control application γ_1 . The resulted optimized configuration (CONF/O) is depicted in Fig. 8d. The values of average QoC and the deviations (terms one and two in Eq. (6)) are 0.0268 and 0.0033, respectively, resulting in a cost function of 0.0301, which is an improvement of 77% over the CONF/SM in Fig. 8c.

VI. EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION

Our proposed optimization strategy, Fog Computing Platform Configuration (FCPC), was implemented in C#, and all the

experiments were run on a laptop with an i7 CPU at 3.0 GHz and 32 GB of RAM. We investigate the performance of our proposed method on ten test cases, which have mixed-criticality tasks. The details of test cases are shown in Table 3, where column 2 shows the total number of cores in the FCP, column 3 shows the total number of control applications, column 4 shows the total number of tasks, and column 5 shows the total number of tasks having a particular criticality level, 0 to 4. Each test case has multiple control applications: Each control application has three control tasks (see Sect. IV-A) and the control task which implements the controller is a LQG controller designed with Jitterbug to control a plant using one of the three different processes which are defined in Eq. (9), Eq. (10), and Eq. (11),

$$G(s) = \frac{300}{s^2 - 200}, \quad (10)$$

$$G(s) = \frac{100}{s^2 + 300}. \quad (11)$$

The tasks in each test case represent real-time tasks with different criticality levels and can be run on any of the cores. Tasks with the same criticality level are mapped to the same partition and overheads are applied to each partition slice.

The results of evaluation are presented in Table 3. The Ω columns show the cost function of test cases for each solution. The results obtained by running FCPC on each test cases are reported in column 6 using the value of the cost function Ω . We have set the weights β_1 , β_2 and β_3 to 0.45, 0.1 and 1.0, respectively. The weights were determined experimentally to guide the search faster towards solutions with optimized QoC . β_1 can be set by analyzing the stability of the control applications with Jitterbug and choosing a value that drives the search towards stable control. Jitterbug also reports the phase margins (smaller phase margin means larger sensitivity) of the applications and β_2 is set to allow a larger deviation from the mean QoC if there is a large variation among the phase margins of the applications. A β_3 value of 1.0 is a relatively large penalty value considering that the cost function terms are in the range [0, 1]. To determine the ability of FCPC to improve the QoC measured by Ω , Table 3 also reports the results obtained by three variants of FCPC, as follows:

- *FCPC/M*: does not optimize the mapping of tasks and uses the mapping determined in the initial solution, as explained in Sect. V-D.
- *FCPC/Q*: does all the optimizations of FCPC but does not use the QoC in the cost function (the first two terms), hence it optimizes only for schedulability, ignoring the control performance.
- *FCPC/P*: generates solutions with our proposed strategy without considering period selection for critical control tasks. The period of control tasks are set to their smallest value.

The other Ω columns show the value in terms of percentage in deterioration of the cost function for FCPC/M, FCPC/Q and FCPC/P, respectively, compared to FCPC. A larger cost

TABLE 3. Evaluation results for our proposed optimization.

Test cases	No. of Cores	Total No. of Control Applications	Total No. of Tasks	Total No. of Tasks for Criticality level of [0-4]	Ω of FCPC	Ω for FCPC/M	Ω for FCPC/Q	Ω for FCPC/P
1	2	2	12	{1,2,2,1,6}	0,19	48%	Not Feasible	60%
2	2	3	23	{3,2,5,4,9}	0,34	5%	Not Feasible	Not Feasible
3	2	2	17	{2,2,4,3,6}	0,21	5%	Not Feasible	33%
4	2	2	23	{2,1,7,6,7}	0,29	13%	Not Feasible	13%
5	3	3	32	{1,4,8,8,11}	0,21	39%	Not Feasible	55%
6	3	3	31	{2,3,9,7,10}	0,22	85%	Not Feasible	50%
7	3	4	33	{4,4,8,7,12}	0,26	15%	Not Feasible	10%
8	4	4	44	{4,6,11,9,14}	0,20	29%	Not Feasible	72%
9	5	6	54	{7,5,14,10,18}	0,21	21%	Not Feasible	Not Feasible
10	6	7	63	{6,7,16,12,22}	0,24	21%	Not Feasible	46%

function value, i.e., larger percentage deterioration, means a worse-quality solution.

As we can see from Table 3, FCPC has been able to obtain feasible solutions for all the test cases, i.e., all the tasks' deadlines are satisfied and all the controllers are stable and have good QoC . The average value of cost function Ω is 0.24 and the values are not highly-deviated in all the test cases. We have used a time limit of 20 to 70 minutes as a termination criteria for FCPC and its variants, depending on the size of the test case.

When comparing FCPC with its variants that ignore certain optimization aspects, we can see in the last three columns of Table 3 large percentage deterioration, or even "unstable" control applications (shown with "Not Feasible") for nearly all the test cases. For example, the results show that not considering QoC in FCPC/Q gives the worst results, which demonstrates that the JITTERTIME-based QoC evaluation of solutions needs to be used during the optimization of a FCP configuration. Otherwise, the controllers become unstable even though the deadlines are not missed. Determining the right period for the control applications is very important as we can see in case of FCPC/P, where considering a single period results in control applications that are unstable and the degradation is high, on average 42% in all other cases. The results also show the importance of mapping, since using in FCPC/M, the mapping determined by the initial solution, the degradation is on the average 28%.

A. REALISTIC TEST CASE

We have evaluated the proposed optimization strategy on a realistic test case which consists of 8 applications running on a fog node inside a vehicle. Future vehicles are envisioned to be "fog nodes on wheels" [33] as they integrate more and more functions and become interconnected with each other.

The details of the test case are in Table 4. We have 8 applications running on a dual-core fog node which include a drive-assistance application for radar-cruise control (application γ_4). The car is modeled with a first-order transfer function and the controller is a LQG speed controller which is design by Jitterbug. Application γ_1 monitors the engine, γ_2 is a passenger comfort application that controls the climate,

TABLE 4. Realistic test case.

Application	Tasks	L	WCET (ms)	T (ms)	D (ms)
γ_1	τ_1	2	0.5	10	10
	τ_2	2	0.5	10	10
	τ_3	2	1	10	10
γ_2	τ_4	1	2	15	15
	τ_5	1	2	15	15
	τ_6	1	1.5	15	15
	τ_7	1	1	15	15
	τ_8	1	2	15	15
γ_3	τ_9	2	1	20	20
	τ_{10}	2	0.5	20	20
	τ_{11}	2	0.5	20	20
	τ_{12}	2	1	20	20
	τ_{13}	2	1.5	20	20
	τ_{14}	2	0.5	20	20
γ_4	τ_{15}	3	0.5	F_4	24
	τ_{16}	3	2.5	F_4	24
	τ_{17}	3	3	F_4	24
	τ_{18}	3	1	F_4	24
	τ_{19}	3	3	F_4	24
	τ_{20}	3	1	F_4	24
	τ_{21}	3	0.5	F_4	24

γ_3 is used for image analysis as part of driver-assistance functionality. We give the applications different critically levels, based on their importance, as presented in the table.

Our proposed optimization strategy has successfully scheduled all the tasks and decided the task mapping to the partitions and cores. The results show that none of the tasks has missed its deadline. Furthermore, the mapping of tasks to the cores shows the core utilization of 86.67% and 86.88% for the dual-core processor. We used JITTERTIME to simulate the controller behavior and calculate the cost of control for the application concerning the given cost function in IV-C with the weights of 0.25, and 0.25 and 1 for β_1 , β_2 and β_3 . The cost function has the value of 0.007.

VII. RELATED WORK

There is already much work on various topics related to Fog Computing [34]–[36]. Even though basic quality-of-service (QoS) for applications has been addressed, the QoC for control applications in the fog is still an open issue. However, there is a lot of useful literature in works that tackle the problem of degradation of control applications [37]–[39].

Researchers propose several approaches (such as partial and spatial separation of control tasks, virtualization of PLCs, scheduling of control tasks, co-design of control applications) that guarantee extra-functional properties of control applications [40]–[43]. The presented approaches are well studied and categorized into a category for platform configuration and a category for the integration of applications. Good performance for control applications will be ensured if both the applications and the platforms are configured.

Separation and isolation of applications regarding criticality levels ensure resource allocation to control applications. Researchers propose spatial and temporal separation to integrate mixed-criticality applications [39], [42], [43]. In this approach, partitions with different criticality levels separate the application. Resources are allocated to the partitions based on the criticality level, which assures resource availability and accessibility for critical applications with high priority. These applications would have guaranteed dependability by promising separation. A presentation of scheduling in mixed-criticality systems, which also considers partitioning, is presented in [44]. For example, Tamas-Selicean *et al.* [45] propose a method in which different Safety-Integrity Levels (SIL) are assigned to the applications. In this method, applications with the same SIL are mapped to a single partition. Each partition is allocated several time slots on a processor to execute respective tasks. Concerning this method, the approach can provide a partition for each control application.

On the other hand, integration of the applications in the platform affects their functional and extra-functional properties. The co-design of control applications configure them at integration level to achieve the highest performance. The co-design approach takes the platform characteristics into account while designing the application to have good integration with the platform.

The QoC analysis and schedulability of the tasks are taken into account while designing the control applications in [46] and [47]. In the proposed approaches, the task scheduler schedules the tasks concerning the QoC of control applications. Besides, co-design is used to determine the period of tasks and design a robust and optimal controller. Other researchers also focused on the co-design and scheduling of control tasks to achieve the maximum QoC for control applications [39], [42], [43]. Co-design and scheduling concerning QoC for control applications are also proposed in the seminal work of Seto *et al.* [26]. The authors optimize the period of control applications concerning the QoC and schedulability of the tasks.

Chwa *et al.* [48] propose a co-design and scheduling method to maximize QoC for control applications. The authors assign a sampling period, and a maximum number of consecutive deadline misses as parameters for each task concerning system stability. Then, the tasks are scheduled concerning the parameters without compromising system stability and also with efficient use of resources. Mahmoud *et al.* [43] use optimization algorithms to derive a timing constraint of control tasks such as the task period to achieve

maximum QoC for the control applications concerning the schedulability of the control tasks [49]. In this work, heuristic algorithms are used to derive the period of tasks, deadlines of the tasks and end-to-end response of the control loop. The assigned parameters are assessed in a simulation that schedules and executes the tasks.

Samii *et al.* [50] present an approach in which a controller is synthesized for each plant, and the control tasks are scheduled concerning the priority of the tasks. In this work, the scheduling is based on the cost of control function, which aims to consider the maximum QoC for all the control applications. The same approach concerning co-design and scheduling of control application is used in [51]. A similar co-design approach is presented by Cervin *et al.* [52]. In this work, the scheduler uses feedback from execution time and also feed-forwards the workload along with the cost of control to achieve the best QoC . Besides, control task parameters such as period are changed with the feedback from execution time. The approach can compensate the impact of jitter on the QoC .

Task scheduling has a significant impact on the performance of control applications. The QoC -aware scheduling reduces the degradation of control applications to some levels based on the criticality of the application. Configuration of the platform at the computation level, especially in the task scheduler guarantees good performance for control applications. Barzegaran *et al.* [21] have presented a heuristic approach for scheduling of tasks and mapping them to the cores which maximizes the QoC of control applications. The work also shows that allowing preemption in scheduling of tasks improves the schedulability of tasks and QoC of control applications. The work does not consider separation of mixed-criticality tasks which is covered in this paper, and it also ignores the effect of control tasks periods on the schedulability, which is also covered in this paper. Task period selection and cost function definition for the optimal control behavior is based on the cost of the control. The scheduling aims to cover the bounded jitter and latency regarding the stability margin of the control applications. In the work by Schneider *et al.* [53], the QoC measurement is embedded in the task scheduler with allowed preemption. The scheduler is capable of handling mixed-criticality applications as well.

Another co-design approach is considered in [54]. The authors get feedback of delay and jitter in the execution of tasks from the scheduler and feed it to the control applications. The controller takes the feedback and adjusts the control output to compensate the delay and jitter impact and to maximize the QoC . The feedback from the task scheduler is also used to predict the jitter and delay. In [55], a feedback scheduling framework is developed to schedule control tasks such that the QoC is maximized for control applications and to adjust workload constraints. The QoC measurement is embedded in the task scheduler. The scheduler gets delay and jitter feedback to change the period of the tasks concerning the QoC and workload management. The same approach is used in [56], to schedule tasks concerning the QoC with

feedback from scheduling. In this work, the period of tasks is changed regarding the feedback. Eker *et al.* [57], propose a similar method. The method uses feedback from the scheduler to assign the period of control tasks. The period assignment provides good control performance along with optimizing the resource allocation of the task.

Cha *et al.* [58] propose a method for scheduling of control tasks which determines the deadline and period of the tasks for achieving maximum *QoC*. The method optimizes the *QoC* of the control applications and resource utilization. In co-design approach presented in [59], the task scheduler guarantees bounded delay and jitter in execution of control application while the co-design approach guarantees that the control application is still stable in the presence of bounded delay and jitter. In work by Fan *et al.* [60], a scheduling algorithm is proposed that can provide some degree of isolation, which can host control applications. In this work, control applications can be assigned to partitions to ensure the separation. The algorithm also maps the tasks to the cores.

VIII. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In this paper, we have addressed the problem of configuring the mapping, partitioning, scheduling and periods of mixed-criticality tasks when implementing the applications on a Fog Computing Platform. The optimized solution has good and balanced Quality-of-Control for critical control applications, ensuring the schedulability of all real-time tasks, as well as spatial and temporal isolation for mixed-criticality tasks. Our proposed strategy is based-on a Simulated Annealing meta-heuristics, which uses an Earliest Deadline First simulation.

We have evaluated this strategy on several test cases. As the results show, our proposed optimization strategy successfully generates solutions which have good and balanced Quality-of-Control for control applications considering temporal isolation for all the test cases in comparison with the solutions that have ignored some of the optimization criteria.

The successful virtualization of control, achieving the same control performance (and dependability) as the one taken for granted in OT, is a crucial step towards the adoption of Fog Computing in the industrial area. In our future work, we will consider the effect of the communication; we will take into account the possibility of incremental scheduling based on our proposed strategy, and we will also consider other optimization techniques such as constraint programming to solve the problem.

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MOHAMMADREZA BARZEGARAN has been a Marie Curie Ph.D. Fellow of computer science with the Technical University of Denmark, since 2018. His research is focused on the configuration of fog computing platform for critical control applications. His main research interests include optimization, the configuration of real-time and safety-critical systems, and co-design of control applications for real-time and safety-critical systems.

ANTON CERVIN (Member, IEEE) received the M.Sc. degree in computer science and technology and the Ph.D. degree in automatic control from Lund University, Sweden, in 1998 and 2003, respectively. He is currently an Associate Professor with the Department of Automatic Control, Lund University, where he does research on event-based estimation and control, autonomous real-time systems, and controller-scheduling co-design.

PAUL POP (Member, IEEE) received the Ph.D. degree in computer systems from Linköping University, in 2003. He has been an Associate Professor with the DTU Compute, Technical University of Denmark, and since 2016, he has also been a Professor of cyber-physical systems. His research is focused on developing methods and tools for the analysis and optimization of dependable embedded systems. In this area, he has published over 130 peer-reviewed articles, 3 books, and 7 book chapters. His research has been highlighted as The Most Influential Papers of 10 Years DATE. He has served as a Technical Program Committee member on several conferences, such as DATE and ESWEK. He received the best paper award at DATE 2005, RTIS 2007, CASES 2009, MECO 2013, and DSD 2016. He also received the EDAA Outstanding Dissertations Award (Co-Supervisor), in 2011. He is also the Chairman of the IEEE Danish Chapter on Embedded Systems. He is also the Director of the DTU's IoT Research Center and has coordinated the Danish National InFinIT Safety-Critical Systems Interest Group.

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